

NOTES

Preparation of Molybdenum Trisulphide by Solid State Interaction between Molybdenum Trioxide and Thiourea

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MOLYBDENUM trisulphide serves as a high density cathode material in alkali metal cells¹⁻³. It can be converted to very pure molybdenum disulphide which is used as a solid lubricating material in nuclear reactors⁴. The present paper describes a solid state reaction between molybdenum trioxide and thiourea at elevated temperature. The mole ratio of the mixture and the temperature at which the reaction is stoichiometric have been investigated.

Results and Discussion

Change of colour of the reaction mixtures of molybdenum trioxide and thiourea kept at 80° and above from yellow to brown indicated the occurrence of chemical reaction, the extent of which could be seen from Table 1. No reaction occurred below 80° and that decomposition of the reaction product took place above 120°. The amounts of MoS₃ were 43.5, 52.48, 63.49, 76.50 and 99.98% of the theoretical amounts at 80, 90, 100, 110 and 120°, respectively. Increase of proportion of thiourea increased the yield of MoS₃ with the increase of temperature in each system. Optimum amounts were obtained in the MoO₃ - thiourea 1 : 3 system at 120°. This indicated the 1 : 3 stoichiometry of

TABLE 1—AMOUNTS OF MoS₃ OBTAINED BY THE INTERACTION BETWEEN MoO₃ AND CS(NH₂)₂

Temp. °C	Mole ratio of MoO ₃ (1.4394 g) to CS(NH ₂) ₂						
	1 : 0.5	1 : 1	1 : 1.5	1 : 2	1 : 2.5	1 : 2.75	1 : 3
80	0.051 4	0.128 0	0.235 2	0.364 8	0.520 0	0.677 6	0.835 2
90	0.059 8	0.152 0	0.283 2	0.441 6	0.640 0	0.818 4	1.008 0
100	0.646 4	0.179 2	0.840 8	0.597 6	0.800 0	0.994 4	1.219 2
110	0.080 2	0.218 0	0.408 0	0.659 2	0.984 0	1.214 4	1.468 8
120	0.099 2	0.256 0	0.528 0	0.825 6	1.280 0	1.672 0	1.919 6

Experimental

A series of mixtures containing MoO₃ and CS(NH₂)₂ (both AnalaR) in the mole ratios 1 : 0.50, 1 : 1, 1 : 1.5, 1 : 2, 1 : 2.5, 1 : 2.75 and 1 : 3 were prepared by intimately mixing MoO₃ (0.01 mol, 1.4394 g) with calculated amounts of CS(NH₂)₂. The mixtures were taken in glass stoppered pyrex tubes and were kept at 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 110 and 120° (±1°) for 1 h while agitating for a number of times.

To evaluate the extent of the reaction, the mixtures were leached with a dilute solution of (NH₄)₂S which dissolved MoS₃ leaving behind other materials in the residue. The solutions were filtered and the amount of MoS₃ (Table 1) were determined by estimating molybdenum colorimetrically⁵. The residues were treated with hot water, filtered and urea in the filtrates estimated by urease method⁶ employing methyl purple as indicator. The insoluble unreacted MoO₃ was dried in an air-oven and weighed.

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Complexes of Manganese(II) with 2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzthiazole

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2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzthiazole (PBT) contains interesting donor sites (N=C-C=N) similar to 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole and 2,2'-dipyridyl and forms

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interesting complexes with some transition metal ions¹. In pursuance of our interest towards structural aspects of the complexes of 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole and related ligands²⁻⁵, we report here the complexes of Mn^{II} with PBT.

Experimental

The ligand PBT was prepared by the reported method⁶. All the other chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

$[Mn(PBT)X_2]$ ($X=Cl$ or Br): An ethanolic solution of Mn^{II} halide (0.01 mol in 50 ml) was refluxed with stoichiometric proportion of the ligand in ethanol on a steam-bath. The complexes separated were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over CaCl₂.

$[Mn(PBT)_2X_2]$ ($X=Cl$ or Br, I and NCS) and $[Mn(PBT)_2(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_2$: Ethanolic solutions of Mn^{II} salts (0.01 mol in 50 ml) were refluxed with ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.02 mol) on a steam-bath for 1 h. The refluxate was concentrated and cooled. The complexes separated gradually. The nitrate salt separated on adding equal volume of ether. The products were collected and dried as stated before. The ir spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr disc in the range 4 000–650 cm⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

Low solubility of the Mn(PBT)X₂ complexes in ethanol, methanol and acetone indicate their polymeric nature. The bis-complexes $[Mn(PBT)_2X_2]$ were fairly soluble in ethanol, methanol and DMF, but were almost insoluble in cold water. In boiling water the complexes dissociated into Mn^{II} salts and free ligand.

The room temperature (309 K) magnetic moments (Table 1) of these Mn^{II} complexes correspond to spin-free octahedral geometry⁷. In case of $[Mn(PBT)_2X_2]$ complexes, six coordination of Mn^{II} was probably achieved through polymerisation involving halide (X) bridging.

Reflectance and absorption spectra of the complexes do not exhibit d-d transition, but they show strong adsorption below 390 nm. In ethanol medium, the ligand exhibits a strong absorption band at 320 nm which shifted to higher wavelength (355 nm) in the complexes indicating the coordination to the metal ion.

The ir spectra of $[Mn(PBT)_2(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_2$ showed nitrate bands at 1 381, 1 270 and 812 cm⁻¹ similar to ionic NO₃⁻ group⁸. A broad ν_{O-H} band at 3 450 cm⁻¹ and a weak and broad δ_{H-O-H} band at 840 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of coordination of water⁹ in this complex. A strong and broad ν_{CN} band around 2075 cm⁻¹ was observed for $[Mn(PBT)_2(NCS)_2]$. The ν_{C-S} and δ_{NCS} bands could not be definitely ascertained due to ligand absorptions. However, from the intensity, position

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF Mn^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff}^* B.M.
	M	N	X	
$[Mn(PBT)Cl_2]$	16.4 (16.2)	8.9 (8.2)	21.1 (20.9)	5.88
$[Mn(PBT)Br_2]$	12.6 (12.8)	6.6 (6.5)	37.5 (37.4)	5.92
$[Mn(PBT)_2Cl_2]$	10.21 (9.98)	10.8 (10.1)	12.7 (12.8)	5.86
$[Mn(PBT)_2Br_2]$	8.7 (8.6)	8.9 (8.7)	24.5 (24.9)	5.87
$[Mn(PBT)_2I_2]$	7.6 (7.5)	7.7 (7.6)	34.8 (34.6)	5.93
$[Mn(PBT)_2(NOS)_2]$	9.4 (9.2)	14.2 (14.1)	—	5.88
$[Mn(PBT)_2(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_2$	8.4 (8.5)	13.46 (13.17)	—	5.90

* At 309 K.

and broadening of the ν_{CN} band, N-bonded thiocyanate group was suggested¹⁰. It is observed that (CSC) band of benzthiazole, assigned at 700 cm⁻¹, is not effected appreciably in its complexes, indicating that benzthiazole 'S' is not involved in bonding. The ligand (PBT) displayed a strong band at 1 612 cm⁻¹ attributable to $\nu_{C=N} + \nu_{C=C}$ vibration. Shifting of this band to lower frequency in the complexes by 10–12 cm⁻¹, indicated the involvement of pyridyl and benzimidazole nitrogens in bonding¹¹. The pyridine ring breathing mode of free ligand (992 cm⁻¹) raised to higher frequencies by 8 to 10 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, suggesting coordination of pyridine nitrogen to the metal ion^{2,12}.

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